

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET FOR UNDER 18

Name of Organisation: Coventry University

Project title: Citizen Scientists Investigating Cookies and App GDPR Compliance (CSI-COP)

Funder: EU Horizon2020 -factsheet page: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873169>

Website: <https://csi-cop.eu/>

Researcher: Dr. Huma Shah

Dear Parent and Guardian, we invite children in your care to volunteer in the CSI-COP project learning about how better to protect their data when using the Internet with a tablet, computer laptop, or when using apps. Your informed consent would allow an **under 18 participant** to learn more by taking a free informal education course '**Your Right to Privacy Online**' and participating in CSI-COP EU Horizon2020 funded international citizen science project led by Coventry University

Completing CSI-COP's free informal education course/MOOC '**Your Right to Privacy Online**' under the guidance of Dr. Huma Shah (who is DBS checked) and her CSI-COP team, it will provide under 18 participants with the practical skills to turn off tracking in websites and apps so better protect personal data.

This course is designed across five easy-to-follow-steps:

1. What is 'privacy'.
2. What is 'personal data'.
3. How is our personal data collected across the internet, and without our knowledge?
4. The charters, regulations and rights we have for the protection of our data online.
5. The free online tools to help us protect our personal data online.

After completing the course your child will be more aware of online tracking technologies, such as third-party cookies, and they will be better able to be in control of their online privacy.

Following completion of the 'Your Right to Privacy' online course, if your child completes a short multiple-choice test they can earn a CSI-COP course certificate. If the topic of online data protection interests your child and they wish to learn more, with your consent your child can join the CSI-COP research team as a volunteer investigating online privacy by exploring cookies in websites visited, and in apps used on a smart phone. Before you decide whether you consent your child or a child under your care to take part as a citizen scientist it is important that you understand why the research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please kindly take the time to read the following information carefully.

What is the purpose of the study?

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is an EU law that requires organisations to safeguard personal data and uphold the privacy rights of anyone in the EU territory. Citizen scientists can play a valuable role in ensuring privacy and providing a better understanding of

what information is tracked online. The CSI-COP project aims at a co-investigation between the professional researchers and citizen scientists interested in human rights in the digital age.

CSI-COP is funded under the EU Horizon2020 scheme:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873169>

CSI-COP project will mobilise citizen scientists from across Europe and beyond to investigate the different types of trackers in websites and smart phone apps. The project offers free training material to informally instruct citizen scientists on 'Your Right to Privacy Online'. With the CSI-COP partners, citizen scientists will be engaged in co-producing a classification of the types of trackers found in web and app investigations. This will lead to the co-creation of an open-access knowledge resource, a repository of digital trackers that can be searched by parents, teachers and more.

Why have children under 18 chosen to take part?

To help children become more aware of the extent of online tracking in websites and apps, and learn about free tools to protect online data and privacy, CSI-COP are extending engagement in the project from adults aged 18 to under 18 participants. Once children complete CSI-COP's free 'Your Right to Privacy Online' informal education course they will be invited to join CSI-COP as volunteer citizen scientists. In this way CSI-COP aims to recruit a wide group of citizen scientists in CSI-COP study to find out the purpose of different cookies in websites and in smart phone apps.

What are the benefits of taking part?

Through participation in this project your child will become aware of their human rights in the digital age. By sharing findings with us about cookies your child finds in the websites visited, and in the apps used on smart phones, your child will be helping Coventry University and the CSI-COP project to better understand the extent of online tracking. Your child will also be contributing to the design of a free-to-access online knowledge-base of cookies found by all the volunteers and CSI-COP researchers.

Are there any risks associated with taking part?

This study is part of the ten international partner CSI-COP project led by Coventry University. It is funded under the EU Horizon2020 SwafS-15-2019 grant agreement 873169: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873169>. The research was granted ethical approval by Coventry University's Research Ethics Committee (application number P139906).

There are no significant risks associated with participation.

Assurances on confidentiality will be strictly adhered to unless evidence of wrongdoing or potential harm is uncovered. In other words, if you or your child tell us something we think that might result in harm or has harmed you, them, or others, Coventry University may be obliged to contact relevant statutory bodies/agencies.

Do under 18 participants have to take part?

No – it is entirely up to you. If you do decide your child can take part, please keep this Information Sheet and complete the accompanying Informed Consent form to show that you understand yours and your children's rights in relation to the research, and that you are happy for your child to participate. Please note down your participant number (which is in the Consent form) and if you seek to withdraw your child from the study at a later date, please email this to Dr. Huma Shah on ab7778@coventry.ac.uk or to Mr Jaimz Winter CSI-COP Creativity Manager / Research Assistant on ad5956@coventry.ac.uk.

You are free to withdraw your child from the project at any time. If you request that your child be withdrawn from engaging in the project then, on request, we will destroy any information collected on your child, even if your child wishes to continue. Information from the project will be destroyed ten years after the conclusion of the project (**30 June 2033**).

Please note, should you wish to contribute your child's experience on the number of tracking cookies uncovered during their CSI-COP engagement there will be an opportunity to co-author publications, including scientific articles. In this case, please inform the CSI-COP researcher you wish to contribute. Hence please note that your child's anonymised data (age; gender; urban vs rural location) may be used in the production of formal research outputs (e.g. journal articles, conference papers, theses and reports) prior to this date. Please be advised to contact Huma at your earliest convenience should you wish to withdraw from the study.

To withdraw, please contact Dr. Huma Shah on ab7778@coventry.ac.uk. Please also contact Coventry University Research Support Office [research.eec@coventry.ac.uk; telephone 44(0)24 7765 7688] so that your request can be dealt with promptly in the event of a researcher's absence. You do not need to give a reason. A decision to withdraw, or not to take part, will not affect you in any way.

What will happen if I decide to allow my under 18 child to take part?

You will be asked a few questions in a survey before your child takes part. The survey is anonymous and follows the 'purpose limitation' principle in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) collecting name and email only in order to issue the CSI-COP free informal education course 'Your Right to Privacy Online' certificate. The survey should take 5-10 minutes to complete.

Data Protection and Confidentiality

Your child's data will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and for citizen scientists in the UK, the Data Protection Act 2018. All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. No sensitive data will be collected. Unless they are fully anonymised in our records, your child's data will be referred to by a unique participant number rather than by name. Your child's data will only be viewed by CSI-COP research team in Coventry University. All electronic data will be stored on a password-protected computer file in Coventry University's servers.

Any paper records will scanned-in to a digital document then stored securely. The paper files will be destroyed securely after the scanning process. Your consent information will be kept

separately from the data you provide about your child's cookie investigations. This in order to minimise risk in the event of a data breach. The lead researcher will take responsibility for data destruction and all collected data will be destroyed on or before 30 June 2033 [10 years after conclusion of CSI-COP].

International Data Transfers

Your child's data will not be stored or processed in any other CSI-COP partner's venue outside the EU. Please be aware for yourself, that countries outside of the European Economic Area may not offer the same level of data privacy protection as in the UK.

Data Protection Rights

Coventry University is a Data Controller for the information provide on your child. You have the right to access information held about your child. Your child's right of access can be exercised in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA 2018). You also have other rights including rights of correction, erasure, objection, and data portability. For more details, including the right to lodge a complaint with the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), please visit www.ico.org.uk. Questions, comments and requests about your personal data can also be sent to the University Data Protection Officer: dpo@coventry.ac.uk

What will happen with the results of this study?

The results of this study may be summarised in published articles, reports and presentations. Quotes or key findings will always be made anonymous in any formal outputs unless we have your prior and explicit written permission to attribute them to you or your child's by name.

Making a Complaint

If you are unhappy with any aspect of this research, please first contact CSI-COP's Director of Science, Dr. Huma Shah, on email: ab7778@coventry.ac.uk. If you still have concerns and wish to make a formal complaint, please write to Dr. Matthew England [Huma's Line Manager] at this email: ab9797@coventry.ac.uk. In your complaint, please provide information about the research project, specify the name of the researcher and detail the nature of your complaint.

CSI-COP invite your child to join the team and help to stop tracking by default across the Internet.

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